

NEGATIVE IMPACTS OF INTERFERENCE ON SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNING: AN ANALYSIS OF CONTRIBUTING FACTORS

Rasulova Istoda Abdulatifovna

Samarkand State University

Abstract. *This article studies the nature and types of interference phenomena, their causes, and analyzes the opinions of various authors on this issue and ways to eliminate interferentive errors in the speech of bilinguals.*

Keywords: *Interlanguage interference, bilingualism, internal interference, external interference, phonetic and grammatical interference*

Introduction

The contemporary sociolinguistic landscape, characterized by increasing multilingualism, demands a reevaluation of foreign language teaching methodologies. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's emphasis on educational reform underscores the urgency of this need. The development of effective strategies to prevent and remediate negative linguistic interference is crucial for preparing students for diverse and globally interconnected environments.

The best option depends on the specific context and intended audience. The original text is a bit rambling; these options aim for greater clarity and conciseness.

The increasing prevalence of multilingualism necessitates a deeper understanding of the factors influencing second language acquisition (SLA) in multilingual contexts. Uzbek primary school students, exposed to Uzbek, Russian, and a foreign language, provide a case study for investigating the impact of prior language learning on subsequent acquisition. The interplay of these languages affects linguistic development, resulting in both positive transfer (facilitation) and negative interference (inhibition). Linguistic interference, defined as the intrusion of features from one language into another, can impede SLA at various linguistic levels, from phonology to syntax and pragmatics. This phenomenon is the result of the dynamic interaction of language systems in the multilingual mind.

Choose the option that best suits your needs and intended audience. The original text contains some redundancy; these rephrased versions aim for greater clarity and conciseness.

In most of cases, interference is realized as the result of language contact, it is to say that, as the result of speaking two or more languages, bilinguals do not follow language norms and get out of them¹.

In order to study interference as a sociolinguistic phenomenon and to prevent the mistakes occurring because of interference a number of works have been completed by world linguists such as U.Weinreich, Ellis, Rod, E.D.Polivanov, Vishnevskaya, Barannikova, L.I.Aliev; and

¹ Вайнрайх У. Одноязычие и многоязычие. В "Новое в лингвистике" / Под ред. В.Ю. Розенцвейга. / Вып. 6. М.: Изд. Прогресс, 1972. -С. 25-60.

by Uzbek linguists like U.K.Yusupov², D.D.Djalolov³, M.Djusupov⁴, G.T.Makhkamova⁵, K.Nabieva⁶, J.Buronov⁷.

When the representatives of two different languages or dialects communicate or write, there occurs inter-lingual communication. In other words, a contact that happens between two or more language owners is a inter-lingual communication. For instance, when the Uzbeks and the Tajiks communicate with each other, i.e. enter into a language contact, there happens Uzbek-Tajik language contact. In this case, if they communicate in Uzbek, Uzbek becomes language of communication. If they speak Tajik, Tajik becomes language of communication. However, they may also communicate with each other in Russian. In this case, Russian is the third language that is used as a mean of communication, and it is called “a lingua franca”. As a result of the language contact, these speakers may get detached or closer. The former situation is called “convergence”, and the latter – “divergence”. For the language contact to happen, one or both sides of the communication must know the native language of the opposite speaker or the lingua franca. Speaking two languages is called “bilingualism”, and the person able to speak two languages is called “bilingual”. A bilingual may transfer the rules of one language into another in a wrong way. This phenomenon is defined as “interference”. Interference usually happens in transferring the rules of the native language into another language.

It is known that teaching a foreign language provides to clarify a subject matter from all perspectives. Based on the existing experiments it is possible to identify and describe the main reasons of interference phenomenon in the range of the system of the following four components:

- linguistic;
- psychological;
- sociolinguistic;
- Stylistic inappropriateness.

To the linguistic factors that indicate appearance and development of interference, primarily belong inappropriateness and similarity of the languages of contact.

According to U.Weinreich, “mixing is always connected to the structure of the language, as if it is a particular answer of the language structure to a strange element that entered into it [9, p. 1]⁸. It is necessary to note that identifying the reason of interference only by similarity or on the contrary by the difference between the structure of the languages is likely to be simplified. It is possible to suppose about the closeness of these concrete structures that they create the most comfortable conditions for the appearance of mixing of the languages that mutually influence each other. The founder of Saratov’s linguistic school L.I.Barannikova said: “From one hand

² У.К.Юсупов. Проблемы сопоставительной лингвистики. Ташкент: Фан, 1987

³ Жалолов Ж.Ж. Тил таълимида методик компрессия ва турли интерференциялар хақида // Хорижий тилларни ўқитиш методикаси ва замонавий тилшуносликнинг долзарб муаммолари. – Андижон: АндУ, 2017.

⁴ Звуковые системы русского и казахского языков. Слог. Интерференция. Обучение произношению / М. Джусупов; М-во нар. образования УзССР, Респ. пед. ин-т рус. яз. и лит. - Ташкент : Фан, 1991. - 239 с.;

⁵ Формирование межкультурной компетенции студентов филологического вуза: (английский язык): автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени доктора педагогических наук: 13.00.05 / Махкамova Гульнара Турдахуновна

⁶Набиева, Карима Методика преодоления межъязыковой лексической интерференции при обучении письменному высказыванию в национальных группах языкового вуза : диссертация ... кандидата педагогических наук

⁷ Ж.Бўронов “Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларининг қиёсий грамматикаси”–Тошкент “Ўқитувчи”, 1973.

⁸Вайнрайх, У. Языковые контакты: состояние и проблемы исследования / пер. с англ. и коммент. Ю. А. Жлуктенко / У. Вайнрайх. – К., 1979

linguistic closeness facilitates the identifies transfer from one language into another, the development of bilingualism and the mixing of languages ... but the closeness of the languages is very limited in it itself. It identifies particular boundaries of language mixing that is connected with numerous similar examples in the structures, because the second appears on the basis of similarity and difference” [2, p. 16]⁹. In this way, it would be honest to denote the reasons of interference as similarities and differences in language structures that mutually influence each other.

Here, without a doubt, the level of formation of the speech skills in the learning language is considered as an additional factor: an imperfect language acquisition form comfortable conditions for the originating interference and contrarily, developing the skills diminishes the level of interference. While analyzing the linguistic reasons of interference, we consider that the criteria like the conditions of the communicative actions, more clearly, the field of contact and the features of its participants is not of little importance. Talking about daily communication, the participants of the contact may ignore to follow the concreteness of pronunciation and some grammatical norms, what about in academic environment, a formal speech provides meaning of speech, concreteness and clearance of its form, and in the result there will be formed a chance to control possible interference. Also, it is purposeful to take into consideration whether a speaker taking part in a communication is a monolingual or bilingual. Bilingualism of the speaker and his awareness of the chance to understand the transfer from language to language or the mixing forms help to appear mixing mistakes in his speech. But monolingualism of the speaker serves to control the correctness of the speech and prevent a potential mixing¹⁰.

As U.Weinreich pointed out that while studying interference it is necessary to take into account the linguistic and extra-linguistic factors [9, p. 1]¹¹. Continuing to define the reasons of interference, we highlight the psychological group and among them we analyze the factor of language ability.

A popular specialist in the fields of psychology and linguistics A.A.Leontyev defines linguistic ability as following: “A language ability is a complex of psychological and physiological conditions that provide the language signs to be assimilated, formed, improved and perceived in a required level by a linguistic community” [6, p. 54]¹². Based on this definition, it is possible to suppose that a weak development of linguistic abilities is one of the main psychological reasons of speech disorder, because in this case the level of accepting and perceiving the rules of one language diminishes for transferring them into another language.

As one of the main features we can also show the connection between the emotional state of the speaker (as well as his tiredness level) and the range of interference. It is reasonable to address the words of U.Weinreich as a proof of our opinion: “To overcome interference demands such actions that are not always easy” [3, p. 54]¹³. Here we must talk about psychological actions and emotional stress which are important to control over the confusions between native and learning languages causing numerous interferentive mistakes.

⁹ Баранникова, Л. И. Вопросы методики преподавания иностранных языков в связи с проблемой языковой интерференции / Л. И. Баранникова. – Саратов, 1966.

¹⁰ Вайнрайх, У. Одноязычие и многоязычие / У. Вайнрайх // Новое в лингвистике. Вып. VI. – М., 1972.

¹¹ Вайнрайх, У. Одноязычие и многоязычие / У. Вайнрайх // Новое в лингвистике. Вып. VI. – М., 1972.

¹² Леонтьев, А. А. *Язык, речь, речевая деятельность* / А. А. Леонтьев. – М., 2010.

¹³ Вайнрайх, У. *Языковые контакты: состояние и проблемы исследования* / пер. с англ. и коммент. Ю. А. Жлуктенко / У. Вайнрайх. – К., 1979.

The existence of psychological and sociolinguistic factors in bilingual's conscience has a syncretic character. In the 50's of the XX century famous American psychologist Ch.Osgood and sociolinguist S.M.Ervin divided bilingualism into two types: "compound" and "coordinate". In order to study this bilingualism phenomenon language acquisition is defined as following: in the case of learning languages in a "mixed" environment (exercising often to move from one language into another, to explain similar meanings), the "compound" type is developed. Turning from language into another when this environment or action changes, is denoted by "coordinate" bilingualism [6, p. 241-253]¹⁴. In the former situation, languages form connected parts of the united system in speaker's conscience. What about the latter type bilingualism, in it the languages form separate existing systems that own important functional independence. Based on this fact, we consider that compound bilingualism can motivate interference to origin and develop more than coordinate bilingualism can.

The sociolinguistic factors that give rise to interference phenomena in a speaker's speech should include, first and foremost, the socio-historical context in which the language is associated.

We support L.I.Barannikova's opinion, she writes as following: "Among the factors influencing the level of development of interference are, first of all, the existence of general socio-historical conditions, the speakers of the languages with which they communicate" [2, p. 12]¹⁵. Except the factors mentioned by the linguist, in our opinion, social status of the language can be expressed by the fact whether the language is given state status, which directly affects its authority and, consequently, its attitude to the purity of language and its compliance with norms.

From this arises the next social relation which we have pointed out. According to Weinreich, "in some societies the transition from language to language is considered normal, while in others it is viewed negatively. If interference is allowed in one language, it is condemned in another". As an example the author shows English-French bilingualism in Canada: the attitude to the state of interference may be in the nature of individual and social phenomena. In Canada, making pronunciation errors (accents) when speaking English are less socially beneficial than in the United States, for example, when a French cleaner speaks English with a French accent, on the contrary, it may be useful in terms of his social background and position [3, p. 53]¹⁶.

Now we analyze methodological factors by identifying such reasons of interference phenomena as linguistic, psychological, sociolinguistic features (as well as, the crossroad of these subfields), firstly, we approach to them and address the teaching method that is shown by this approach. A practical and comparative study, the most wide-spread method among the group of the methods based on the conscious approach, gives a little a chance for interference. For the influence of one language on another to be less, it is purposeful to study similarities and differences between the structures of native and foreign languages. Perfect knowledge of one's native language serves as an important factor in learning a foreign language.

Thereby, interference is produced mainly in presence of four aspects – language norms, bilingual's character, relationships between native and foreign languages, social conditions. Based on these aspects, there was created a four-dimensional typology of interference:

¹⁴ Weinreich, U. Languages in contact / U. Weinreich. – N. Y., 1953. – P. 1

¹⁵ Баранникова, Л. И. Вопросы методики преподавания иностранных языков в связи с проблемой языковой интерференции / Л. И. Баранникова. – Саратов, 1966.

¹⁶ Вайнрайх, У. Языковые контакты: состояние и проблемы исследования / пер. с англ. и коммент. Ю. А. Жлуктенко / У. Вайнрайх. – К., 1979.

Based on these aspects, they created the following four-dimensional typology of interference:

- 1) due to deviation from the language norms (linguistic aspect);
- 2) according to the specifics of the speech activity of the bilingual (psychological aspect);
- 3) according to the relationship between the native language and the languages studied (inter-linguistic aspect);
- 4) according to the social situation (socio-ethnolinguistic aspect)¹⁷.

Interference is a phenomenon that is not up to the will of the speaker. Its amount corresponds to the increase of person's acquisition of language and it totally disappears when the language is fully mastered. The structural reason of interference depends on the differences at each level of two languages, while the nonstructural reasons are equivalent to the psychological laws of inter-lingual equality. Of all the events that occur as a result of language interactions (interference, transference, intercalation, translocation), only interference can be predicted, i.e., a linguist can target an interference phenomenon as the result identifying similarities and differences by comparing two languages. Other phenomena are unpredictable as their formation depends on the influence of many extra-linguistic aspects.

Regarding interference G.M.Vishnevskaya argues that as a result and process of the influence of the language system on bilingual's speech, one language system becomes dominant, and this effectively affects the system of the second learned language.¹⁸

For example, in Uzbek word "tulki" (fox) there is no need to put a soft sign after the letter "l", though it is pronounced softly. But if the Russians want to write this word, they write and pronounce it like this: "тульки". Such kind of misunderstandings cause difficulties in learning language.

It is important to study the didactic and psychological aspects of not only the theoretical problems of phonetic interference (reasons of origin, types), but also preventing and overcoming potential mistakes. In particular, Methodist K.Kadyrova in teaching Arabic to Uzbek students to explain the reasons of phonetic interference, addresses O.A.Yamshchikova's following opinion: "Phonetic interference is the result of an effective influence of particular skills system as a leader on the skills acquired later. One of the main features of phonetic interference as a psychological phenomenon in the methodology of teaching another language is the violation of auditory-pronunciation skills as a result of interactions and the opposite perception of the phonetic system of the studied language.

Methodist scholar V.S.Dmitreyeva quotes N.S.Trubetskoy's opinion, who paid special attention to the problems of bilingualism in the field of linguistics: "In the process of listening and analyzing speech, we usually use our phonological "filters", which are primarily considered in our native language. The fact that our "filters" do not correspond to that of another language (which, of course), leads to a number of errors and misunderstandings. The sounds of other language accept the wrong phonological interference of our language.¹⁹ So, an accent in a foreign language is not an inability to pronounce this or that sound, but it is connected to "the

¹⁷ Карлинский А.Е. Экспериментальное изучение лексической интерференции в прикладных целях // - Алма-Ата, 1989, с.60.

¹⁸ Вишневская, Г.М. Билингвизм и его аспекты [Текст] / Г.М. Вишневская. – Иваново, 1997. – 100 с. 5,с24

¹⁹ Дмитриева, Ю.В. Проблема межъязыковой интерференции в преподавании иностранных языков в вузе Электронный ресурс. / Ю.В. Дмитриева. Сайт Саратовского государственного университета имени 49. Н.Г. Чернышевского. Режим доступа: <http://www.sgu.rti/files/nodes/13579/Dmitrieva.doc>. - Загл. с экрана

wrong conclusion about the sounds” based on differences between the phonological systems of native and foreign languages.

In the early stages of language learning, the sounds of foreign language are learned side by side with those of native language. A relatively common type of phonetic interference is similarity-based interference, and it is usually connected to a direct transition of native language pronunciation skills to similar foreign sounds while acquiring the sound system of studied language.

Methodists divide skills into three groups:

- 1) Transferring speech skills of native language into the data of a new language;
- 2) Transferring previously acquired skills into the data of a new language;
- 3) Newly acquired skills.

According to S.G.Nikolaev²⁰, it is possible to make a conclusion that there are three approaches in teaching foreign languages taking into account the features of native language:

- 1) To compare the facts and similarities of the two languages, and to acquire by means of the similarities;
- 2) To compare the facts of the two languages and to set the similarities, and to acquire by means of differences;
- 3) To compare the facts of the two languages and to set the incompatible ones, and to acquire by means of contrast.

We can use all aforementioned three approaches, if we take Uzbek as a native language, and Turkish as a foreign language. Both languages belong to the same language family, and therefore, they have common features. But Uzbek and Russian belong to different language families, thus there should be paid more attention to many different features in these languages.

While teaching children to the second language, it is important to take into account the experience of teaching speech in native language. For example, acquiring separate sounds articulation is the most difficult task for a child. O.I.Solovyeva pointing out the main directions of developing the sound culture of speech, argues that the educator has the task to teach children to pronounce the sounds in words clearly, to pronounce words correctly in accordance with the rules of orthoepy of the language, to teach them to cultivate an expressive speech.²¹

Thus, it is significant to pay attention, firstly, to hearing correctly and pronouncing clearly. Only if we pronounce the sounds purely and correctly, the process of learning a language becomes easy.

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²⁰ Николаев, С.Г. К вопросу о грамматической интерференции и путях ее преодоления в рамках курса интенсивного обучения [Текст] / С.Г. Николаев // Интенсивное обучение иностранным языкам. – М.: Изд-во МГУ, 1990. 7-14 с.

²¹ Соловьёва О.И. Методика развития речи и обучения родному языку в детском саду. 3-нашр. М., 1996, б. 50-51.

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